

Supporting Information to:

Preparation and surface functionalization of a tuneable porous system featuring stacked spheres in cylindrical pores

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Figure S1. Assembly of PS spheres at high concentration and high flow rate. **(a)** Top view: Agglomeration of PS spheres on the outer surface of the AAO sample, reducing the packing along the pores; **(b)** Cross-section view.

Figure S2. AFM images and roughness values of the HfO₂ and ZnO layers on Si wafers before and after streaming current studies. Increase in roughness due to slight solubility in alkaline regimes.

(Kr adsorption data here!)

Figure S3. Sorption isotherms.